

THE LEXICAL-SEMANTIC STRUCTURE OF LINGUISTIC CHANGING IN GERMAN LANGUAGES

Abstract

The article explores how language changes affect our understanding of the world, specifically in Germanic languages. However, the analysis compares how different language systems perform in terms of linguistic changes. The article presents the results of detecting changes in German vocabulary and meaning, using an evaluation framework. The article examines the definition of lexical-semantic structure compatibility and students' understanding of the multicultural language world in the German language, as well as the main factors that influence the development of these structures. It analyzes previous studies on linguistic awareness in the fields of linguistics, lexical-semantic features, and psycholinguistics, and presents the results of research on the understanding of linguistic awareness among speakers of German. The findings prove that both linguistic and cultural phenomena influence the position of the component in the semantic field, forming its core and periphery. It is noteworthy that these terms stand out from other neologisms due to their ability to more accurately reflect events in the world and German speakers' attitudes towards them.

Keywords: speech act, linguistic consciousness, lexical-semantic changes, multicultural world, communication skills, semantic meanings

Introduction

Elements of speech act

Speech act theory posits that communication aims to achieve specific goals and that every word represents a speech act. Linguistic phenomena in speech act are represented by symbolism, metaphorization, and word formation, while cultural phenomena are represented

by geographical location and practical communication skills.

Speech act theory (Aikhenvald, Alexandra Y. 2020; Stepanova, M. 2007) is a central concept in the field of pragmatics, and has been the subject of study for linguists for quite some time. Elements of culture in a speech act include symbols, language, norms, values, and artifacts [1; 2].

Figure 1. Speech act elements (Humbolt 2014)

Language enables effective social interaction and shapes our understanding of concepts and objects (Humboldt W.2000). Linguistic organization refers to the linguistic principles governing the repeated regularities in the language of communication described by linguistic theories [3, p.57].

Pragmatics, in its most general form, examines the role of linguistic changes in speech, and specifically focuses on the attitudes of the speakers towards these changes and how they affect the listeners. (Humboldt, 2000) a German linguist who studied mental activity in a multicultural world, emphasized that the speech of each individual should be subject to lexical-semantic compatibility in pragmatic, formed in the process of mutual speech. It is known that the mentality and outlook of people living in different countries are formed by vital linguistic tasks [6 p.112].

According to Humboldt, lexical coherence was central in speech acts. Whorf, in his works, pays attention to the effect of language on various aspects of human activity, following general language laws and

their reflection in various phenomena. Researchers (Aikhenvald, 2020, Pavlenko. 2008.) conducting discussions and research on language problems provide a conceptual interpretation of national language consciousness in the development of linguistic personality in a multicultural world [1; 6]. Such studies aim to understand the characteristics of speech habits, additional interpretations of meaning, and political, cultural, and historical connotations of language units and speech. These studies follow the anthropocentric point of view.

Linguistic changing in the language

In recent times, economic growth and political decentralization have led to the development of various regional dialects in German (Müller, 2005; Schmidt, 2005). This has caused a shift in the phonology structure, resulting in a multicultural aspect of the German language. Specifically, the vowel sounds have weakened, and articles have become essential for conveying the case of nouns when speaking German. Languages undergo changes in their pronunciation,

word forms, syntax, and semantic meanings, which are mostly gradual and noticeable over several generations [11, 13].

The German language has enriched its vocabulary through the process of word formation. As the language evolved, some words disappeared, while others appeared, and the meaning and stylistic status of some words changed. Recent studies (Dubossarsky, 2017; Meibauer 2001) proved that historical lexicology shows that modern words come from the real material in the language and its models. In modern times, the German language has developed its vocabulary by creating new words, changing the meanings of existing words, introducing homonyms, and borrowing from

other languages. Each of these ways of enriching the language has its own characteristics [5; 10].

The formation of new words and changes in meaning have contributed new words to the dictionary, while borrowing from other languages has also enriched the German vocabulary. Changes in language can manifest in updates to the principles of lexical compatibility. Linguistic changes can occur due to various non-linguistic reasons and can result in the creation of new words, popular sayings, and terms (Duden 2000). Such changes in language can also bring about changes in communication and socio-cultural norms [3; 4].

Figure 2. Linguistic changing in German language (Duden 2014)

Language change is a phenomenon that occurs constantly, sometimes without us even noticing it. In this article, we will delve into the concept of language change specifically in the context of the English language. We will examine the various ways in which a language can evolve over time, and the factors that drive these changes (Schmidt, 2005; Rozen 2005). Additionally, we will explore the impact of language change on us as individuals and as a society [13;15].

The diversity of languages is equal to that of language shift. The process of changing one's language is intricate and may involve *social, cultural and historical* variables. Language changes can be influenced by a variety of linguistic factors, including grammar, pronunciation, and register. Throughout history, language has undergone various changes in different forms. Sound, lexical, semantic, and syntactic changes are some of the types of language change that have occurred over time. These changes have contributed to the evolution of languages and have influenced the way people communicate with each other.

Stem-Changing Verbs List by phonologically:

- geben: to give (changes from "e" to "i")
- nehmen: to take (changes from "e" to "i")
- fahren: to drive (changes from "a" to "ä")

- laufen: to run (changes from "a" to "ä")
- tragen: to carry (changes from "a" to "ä")
- sehen: to see (changes from "e" to "ie")
- lesen: to read (changes from "e" to "ie")

<https://www.google.com/search?q=llist+of+word+s+changing+in+german+language>

Linguistic factors

Linguistic factors that occur within the language system are the source of semantic change. Such natural language changes typically take longer than those caused by causes outside the language system. Researchers (Weinreich, 1953. Seidenberg, 2004) stated that This phenomenon has been observed throughout history; for example, the transformation of Old German to Middle German took centuries [18; 19].

Linguistic factors can include:

- *Linguistic changes / causes*
- *Metonymy / metaphor*
- *Ellipses*
- *Excessive length*
- *Wordplay and puns*
- *Disguising language / misnomers (i.e. an inaccurate name)*

Several references (Kulkarni, 1990; Perozzi, 2014) examined that metonymy is a figure of speech that substitutes the name of an object with an attribute

or adjective. For example, in horse racing, tracks are commonly referred to as 'turfs' [12; 16].

Metaphors can also influence word associations. It is a technique in which word meanings are expanded to demonstrate a link between two similar things.

Ellipsis is the process of repeatedly using two words together in a sentence until they have the same meaning. For example, the term "starve" originally meant "to die." However, when it was frequently used in sentences about hunger, its meaning shifted to "to die of hunger."

Several factors can influence semantic shifts within these causes. The table below provides examples of extralinguistic and linguistic causes of semantic change.

Lexical-semantic changes of words

A lexical change is a kind of language change that can involve changing a word for a specific referent or

even changing a lexeme in the idea it conveys. Its closest linguistic relatives are other West Germanic tongues, such as Scots, Afrikaans, Dutch, English, and the languages of the Frisian region. Additionally, its vocabulary bears a strong resemblance to that of several North Germanic languages, including Danish, Norwegian, and Swedish (František, 2014; Pavlenko, 2008) [16; 17]. Some German words that are so widely used in English that you might not even realize they are German have been borrowed by English speakers: *Kindergarten*, *Doppelgänger*, *Gestalt*, and *Wanderlust*. You will still need to dedicate the same amount of time to learning new terms as you would for any other language because the vocabulary is still very different.

Several borrowing words from German language included English dictionary

Table 2.

The words borrowing from German language

The words borrowed from German:	
1	Angst [æŋkst].
2	Rucksack
3	Blitz
4	Hamster
5	Noodle (from German 'Nudel')
6	Abseil (from German 'abseilen')
7	Kindergarten ['kɪndərˌɡɑːdn̩].
8	Wunderkind ['vʊndərˌkɪnd].
9	Zeitgeist ['tsaɪtɡaɪst].
10	Schadenfreude [ˈʃɑːdənˌfrɔɪdə].
11	Hinterland ['hɪntərˌlænd].
12	Über ['uːbər].
13	Wanderlust ['wɑːndərˌlʌst].

English was found to have a lexical similarity of 60% with German and 27% with French using this method. One can assess the degree of genetic relatedness between two languages using lexical similarity [20; 21].

The vocabulary of any language is highly dynamic and changeable in terms of location. Since words convey significant information, they reflect all the transformations that occur in society over time. Words are similar to living beings in some ways - they come into existence, grow, interact with other language elements on different levels, become obsolete, or "die" out. It would be interesting to examine the changes in individual lexical and semantic processes in modern German language over the last ten years since Germany reunited, and the integration of Europe was completed, leading to the establishment of new political and economic circumstances that resulted in the emergence of a new education system.

The focus of this article is on the lexical units in the German language related to the integration of Europe into the EU and the unification of Germany. It is widely known that natural languages undergo evolution, and words tend to change their meanings over time (Meibauer, 2001) [10 p.208]. The increasing use of digital text resources in education is leading to the emergence of new semantic changes in texts (Kulkarni, 2014). Other interesting phenomena will

also be mentioned, such as colloquial versions of official designations and fashionable terms [16 p.24].

Numerous German linguists, both local and foreign, have contributed significantly to the study of word formation. As cited by Schmidt, (2005) along with borrowing, word formation is the most crucial way of expanding the vocabulary of any language. Word-building structures are created by using morphemic and lexical elements in accordance with the analogy (models and patterns) of already-existing lexemes. Various researchers have proposed multiple models of word-building structures, and the linguistic field lacks a single interpretation and definition of the word-formation model as a unit of word-formation. These models differ in several ways among researchers, as noted by Stepanova in 2007. The categories of word-building structures are determined by the types of word-forming components, their combinations, and the resulting word-formative meaning. The evolution of word formation does not involve the emergence of new ways of word formation but rather the preferred use of one or more models, as further explained by Stepanova in 2007 [2; 13].

As a dominant language, the replacement of old lexical meanings with new ones in the English language demonstrates its power weakly in the reciprocal effect. Recent cites (Dubossarsky, 2017) examine that the changes in the lexical-semantic groups of *synonyms*,

antonyms, poly-semes, homophones, etc. on the levels included in the dictionary should be reflected in the language consciousness [5 p.846]. The changing of simple-level words at progressively different levels highlights the advantages of linguistic change. While some endangered languages use one word to express what they traditionally express in two or more words, the preference of more endangered languages for one word in language contact creates a contradiction in multicultural understanding. One aspect of language evolution is that changes in the meaning of a word happen alongside changes in life. This is known as semantic change and can occur in various areas. Lexical change, on the other hand, refers to the loss of certain words and the addition of new ones to the vocabulary over time.

Countless bilingualism and heritage language studies, (Cotelova 2010; Polinsky 2008; Pavlenko 2008; Weinreich 1953), make it necessary to conduct psycholinguistic analyses in solving this problem [8; 14; 17]. In addition, the lack of a conceptual map of the different characteristics of the words and phrases that have been created creates confusion in communication (Pavlenko, 2008). Furthermore, not all words are affected in the same way; each word has its life trajectory [6; 17].

It's important to keep in mind that the process of semantic change in linguistics is gradual. The meaning of a word can change based on shifts in society, economics, and culture. Changes are made based on how well they fit into the current lexicon, using up-to-date terminology while still preserving the original meaning in a practical sense.

The causes of semantic change in language have been somewhat neglected in comparison to its classifications (Duden, 2000; Eins, 2009). Although opinions on this topic are scattered throughout linguistic works, they have never been collected into a complete source. However, understanding the reasons behind semantic change is crucial since it plays a significant role in interpreting language development. Vocabulary is the most flexible aspect of language and its semantics are quick to respond to changes in human activity, regardless of the field [3; 4; 5; 7].

Semantic change is often influenced by changes in social values. This means that different ethnic or social groups may experience changes in meaning differently for different words. These are extralinguistic causes (not involving language) and linguistic causes (involving language). These are extralinguistic causes (not involving language) and linguistic causes (involving language).

A German database has been created that contains norms for semantic typicality, age of acquisition, and concept familiarity for 824 exemplars of 11 semantic categories. These categories include four natural categories such as TIERE, VÖGEL, FRÜCHTE, and GEMÜSE, and five man-made categories such as KLEIDUNG, MÖBEL, FAHRZEUGE, WERKZEUGE, and MUSIK INSTRUMENTE. BERUFE and SPORT were also included. The database underwent lexical changes during development [20; 21].

The effects of semantic category and the correlations between word length, word frequency, semantic typicality, age of acquisition, and concept familiarity are discussed, along with reliability data and additional analyses. High inters and interstudy reliabilities are generally seen in the data, offering researchers a new tool for planning studies using German word materials.

Various factors can influence the speed and accuracy of lexical-semantic processing in healthy individuals. These factors include semantic typicality, age of acquisition, and concept familiarity. Typically, researchers (Müller, 2005) evaluate these variables by asking participants about the age when they learned a word, how familiar a concept is to them, or how well a word represents a particular semantic category. Additionally, intrinsic factors, such as word length (measured in syllables, phonemes, or letters), can also affect word processing [11 p.126]

It's interesting to note that the age at which we learn a word, also known as the age of acquisition, can have an impact on how we process it. One theory is that concepts we learn at an earlier age may serve as a foundation for later learning, making them more familiar and frequently used. According to Zevin and Seidenberg's (2002) studies this can be explained by the fact that early-acquired concepts have a higher cumulative frequency of associated words or different frequency trajectories [18 p.31]

Extralinguistic causes. The extralinguistic causes of semantic change are primarily social or historical in nature. If we break down the term "extralinguistic", we can see that it refers to "extra" factors that exist outside of the language itself. Scientist Linguist Andreas Blank (2020) divides this factor into three major subcategories:

Psychological factors are those that influence how people perceive words and their meanings. If a word's original meaning is unclear, it is given a new interpretation. The meaning of a word may also become *taboo* or be used as an euphemism; e.g., the term 'pass away' can be used to describe someone dying.

Sociocultural factors are among the most common extralinguistic causes of semantic change. A country's social, economic, or political status can change dramatically, influencing semantics. For example, the meaning of words changed significantly following the Industrial Revolution. For example, the term 'engine' evolved from describing general wartime devices to referring to a specific mechanical device. This change in meaning represents semantic change, specifically narrowing.

Cultural and encyclopedic factors

These factors refer to the cultural reasons why a word's meaning can change. This could be due to cultural changes that affect how the word is classified (resulting in a semantic change). For example, the term 'cool' was originally used in jazz music, but as jazz's popularity grew, the word became associated with anything trendy.

Lexical-semantic modification in linguistic neologism

In the group of Germanic languages, factors like lexical frequency and ambiguity play a significant role in shaping language awareness. The influence of language contact in the multicultural world is also impacted by external factors of the language, and this process is speeding up.

The lexical composition of a language is an extremely flexible and extensive system that can move and change due to many factors, one of the most important of which is the social environment. Every year, a large number of neologisms appear in developed languages, most of which are associated with certain events that occurred in the world or country [12; 113; 14].

It is known that one method for replenishing vocabulary is through neologisms. These are "words, word meanings, or combinations of words that appeared at a specific time in any language or were used once ("occasionally") in any text or act of speech. The classification of words as neologisms.

Kratochvíl, František (2014) states that many new words or neologisms, appear in established languages because of the need to name new things and to understand them. Several factors contribute to the creation of neologisms within languages, including intralingual factors such as economy, unification, systematization of linguistic means, variation of nominations with different internal forms, etymology, expressive-emotional tasks, and stylistic expressiveness. Some neologisms may eventually be accepted and absorbed into the language over time, becoming full-fledged lexical units that are no longer considered neologisms. The crucial element in defining a neologism is the concept of "novelty." According to E.V. Rosen, a word can still be considered a neologism if it carries with it a connotation of novelty, which may fade over time. [15 p.192]

The following words were ranked by the German Language Society in 2021 (GfdS2):

1) **Wellenbrecher** ("breakwater"): refers to the measures taken to prevent the fourth wave of the coronavirus pandemic.

2) **Solidarität** ("solidarity"): a combination of the word "Solidarität" and the name of the river Ahr (Ar), originally used to assist owners of flood-damaged vineyards. Now it also means willingness to help by donating and providing active support, even outside the affected region.

3) **Pflox** (from Pflege ("care") and Exit ("departure"), similar to Grexit, Brexit, etc.): refers to the departure of junior medical personnel from the profession due to low wages and difficult working conditions.

4) **Impfpflicht** ("compulsory vaccination").

5) **Ampelparteien** ("traffic light parties"), named after the colors of the parties of the coalition formed after the 2021 Federal elections in Germany (red for SPD, yellow for FDP, and green for Greens).

6) **Lockdown-Kinder** ("children in quarantine"): refers to the stress of modern children who have been studying online for almost two years during the pandemic.

7) **Booster** ("booster"): refers to booster vaccination (re-vaccination) to protect against coronavirus.

8) **freitesten**: means bypassing coronavirus restrictions using a coronavirus test for unvaccinated and not recovered people.

9) **Triell** ("trial"): refers to a duel "for three", associated with the 2021 election campaign.

10) **fünf nach zwölf** ("five after twelve"): refers to the need for action in any context, such as climate, politics, and the fight against a pandemic. This phrase is a transformation of the well-known expression "fünf vor zwölf" ("at the last moment"), and the transformed combination means that it was necessary to start acting earlier [21; 22].

It can be assumed that the German language is highly capable of creating new words using its own means. As mentioned earlier, only one in ten German words is directly borrowed from English. The rest are created using composites - complex words made up of several roots. The word "Pflöxit," which came in third place, is an example of a composite word that borrows a component from English. This word is commonly associated with certain phenomena such as "Grexit" and "Brexit" and has specific connotations. In essence, it is difficult to find a word that has a similar meaning and connotation without using the "exit" component.

Conclusion.

In the end, the development of lexical compliance involves a large process that includes lexical-semantic change. The study report agreed that when altering lexical-semantic processes, speech act components should be taken into account.

The first stage in this process is linguistic change, which can arise for a variety of non-linguistic reasons. Based on the following socio-cultural norms, these changes influence word formation, cultural views and communication.

Semantic change originates in the language system due to linguistic factors. These shifts in natural language typically occur more gradually than those caused by outside factors.

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